

during both wet and dry seasons, but dry season rates were only about 50% of those in the wet season. This may be due to a rise in groundwater table during the monsoon period. Initial concentrations of ammoniacal and nitrate N were high, gradually dropping within 15 d after application of N (see table). N loss increased with increasing water depth. N loss in the dry season was about 50% of loss in the wet season. □

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and loss of water and N.^a Thanjavur, India, 1985-87 wet and dry seasons.

Water depth (cm)	Wet season				Dry season			
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)		Grain yield (t/ha)	Water loss (mm)	N loss (kg/ha)	
			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻			NH ₄ ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻
2.5	6.4	373	4.6	1.3	4.6	196	2.2	0.6
5.0	6.6	448	5.5	1.6	4.7	238	2.7	0.8
7.5	6.2	516	6.2	1.8	4.4	265	3.0	0.9
LSD (0.05)	ns				0.1			

^aAv for 3 yr.

Effect of irrigation schedule on grain yield and water use efficiency in transplanted rice

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Five levels of irrigation (see table) were laid out in randomized block design with four replications.

Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 6.8, EC 0.28 dS/m, 0.58% organic C, with 185, 18, and 250 kg available N, P, and K/ha. Test variety was IR36.

Water applied 1 or 3 d after

Effect of irrigation schedule on rice grain yield, water requirement, and water use efficiency. Ambikapur, India, 1987 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Effective rainfall (cm)	Water requirement (cm)	Water use efficiency (kg/ha per cm)
Continuous submergence 5 ± 2 cm water (CS)	3.7	36	126	29
Application of 7 cm water 1 DAD	3.7	43	113	32
Application of 7 cm water 3 DAD	3.5	46	88	40
Application of 7 cm water 5 DAD	3.4	47	82	41
Rainfed with provision to store all rainwater (RF)	3.1	74	74	42
LSD (0.05)	0.2			

disappearance of ponded water (DAD) was as good as continuous submergence (CS) in grain yield and

significantly superior to rainfed (RF). Irrigation 3 DAD saved 38 cm water without sacrificing yield. □

Farm machinery

A root zone liquid urea applicator for wetland rice

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A simple root zone liquid applicator attachment to the hand compression insecticide sprayer was developed in 1984 (see figure). Prilled urea dissolved in water (1:2 ratio) is kept under pressure in the sprayer tank. The applicator is attached in place of the insecticide lance rod using an adaptor pipe with matching threads.

The operator lifts the applicator with the right hand and gently pushes the lower ends of eight branch nozzles

Urea solution application using root zone liquid applicator attachment to hand compression sprayer. AP, India, 1984-1986.